

RESEARCH PAPER

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Ethnobotanical profiling of vegetative flora of Hajira Village Kalpur (Davigali) Union Council, Banteeni District Poonch Azad Kashmir

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Abstract

This research survey was originated with the aim to explore the knowledge of indigenous medicinal plants of Hajira village Kalpur (Davigali) District Poonch Azad Kashmir. The study was conducted from June 2022 to October 2022. The field trips were conducted and information was taken from the local people of selected area using structure and semi structured in individual and group discussion. Information was gathered on 30 plants belonging to 20 different families. Most of the plants have multiple local uses. Various quantities indices such as Family contribution, Mode of administration and plant parts were used to obtain the suitable information. Among families, the contribution of Rosaceae was highest (20%). In mode of administration extract, powder showed great contribution of 13% while contribution of leaves, fruits was 20% and in diseases category, 32 diseases were treated including antidiabetic (8%), Cancer and Urinary infection (7%). The present research provides valuable information on important medicinal flora of Hajira village Kalpur (Davigali) District Poonch Azad Kashmir. This study concluded that the studied area has diverse vegetation and have good potential for ethno botanical aspects.

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Introduction

Ethnobotany is the systematic knowledge of plants in local culture and their application in traditional pharmaceutical industry (Jennings *et al.*, 2014). Humans meet their need by plants i.e. medicine, food, fuel, shelter and fodder for animals (Towns and Van-Andel, 2016). Ethnobotanical investigation on wild and domesticated plants has significant value in medicinal aspects (Sanssanelli *et al.*, 2017; Faruque *et al.*, 2018). The main goal of ethnobotany is to document the new curative knowledge of threatened species and preserve them for future use (Ajaib *et al.*, 2014). The therapeutic plants extract has been applied for screening of new drugs to treat human diseases (Alarcon *et al.*, 2015; Ahmad *et al.*, 2017). Low economic condition of human population is the current demand for using medicinal plants instead of synthetic medicines (Aziz *et al.*, 2017). In addition, considerable potential of natural sources as compared to adverse and high cost effects of synthetic drugs (Hussain *et al.*, 2019).

Ethno botany correlates the plants with indigenous people and their social and cultural environment. John Harshberger introduced ethnobotany firstly in 1896. Though, the ethnobotany began long, in ancient times (Mahmood *et al.*, 2011; Arshad *et al.*, 2014; Amjad *et al.*, 2014). Taxonomists, pharmacologists, ecologists, watershed and wild life managers are using indigenous medicinal information of plants to improve the affluence of a particular region besides listing the traditional or local uses (Ibrar *et al.*, 2007). In Pakistan for curative purposes numbers of plants are being used by local communities (Bibi *et al.*, 2008). According to Hocking, 84% of Pakistan's population is relying on traditional medicines for their primary health protection (Amjad *et al.*, 2015).

Since with the beginning of human development, there is a significant role of medicinal plants (Kayani *et al.*, 2014; Amjad *et al.*, 2017). The native and traditional knowledge of outmoded drugs are used in scientific discipline for several centuries (Baydoun *et al.*, 2015). By the rapid development in modern drugs and technique to cure health problem decline the traditional knowledge, with the passage of time

utilization of plants in modern medicine has increased but the traditional system still succeeds in the rural communities (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012). New studies and researches on the ethnobotany provide several ways for the invention of modern drugs (Amjad *et al.*, 2017). Unfortunately, only hakims are associated with medicinal plants, there must be a great attention to the ethnobotanical aspects of plants at government level (Shinwari *et al.*, 2000).

Azad Jammu & Kashmir is a hilly area having diverse climate, soil and habitat type naturally. Number of plants specifically present in this area which have medicinal importance while previous studies show specific culture of Azad Kashmir and people with lot of knowledge about local herbal plants (Ahmed *et al.*, 2009). Kalpur is situated at the east of city Hajira and it is one of the most prominent villages of Hajira District Poonch. This is the first effort in village Kalpur union council Banteeni to provide ethnobotanical uses of different plants by local people. Moreover, the area is abundant in useful plants because of its sustainable environment but this area is remained unfamiliar due lack of resources and knowledge. This study report examines the traditional knowledge on the utilization of the medicinal plants from the Hajira village Kalpur (Davigali) District Poonch Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. This research will contribute on the conservation and sustainable use of the natural resources of this area.

Materials and methods

Study area

Kashmir is a State that is governed by two countries: India and Pakistan. Pakistani administrated part is known as Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK). Hajira is the one of the developed city of District Poonch AJK. It is located at 33.45° to 59.99° north latitude and 73.53° to 59.99° east longitude. Kalpur is a village near Davi Gali and Davi Gali has historical background, Plangi fort is present here. It is located 8 km from Hajira, 12 kilometers from Banjonsa, and 32 km from Rawalakot an altitude of 5,480 feet (Fig. 1). Davi Gali has green grassy lands surrounded by pine forest and mountains. The name Devi Gali is linked to this area's history.

Fig. 1. Map of study area

Vegetative survey

In June 2022 many field trips were arranged to the area for collecting information about the local traditional uses of plants. The medicinal knowledge was collected from old knowledgeable people and local hakeems. Information on the local uses, recipes, etc., was gathered through open-ended questionnaires and by interviews. The distance between sampling points were 10 and 20 km within the hills. The information was considered reliable and reported when at least 10 interviewees attested to the name and usage of the plants.

Data collection

Duration for collection of Plants were from June 2022 to October 2022. Total 30 informants were selected randomly contains 11 male and 19 females. The age of the informant fluctuated from 50 to 80 years. They comprised several Hakeems (Traditional doctors) who were interviewed in order to record the local house hold recipes for the preparation of medicines. Detail of informants is provided in Table 1.

Identification and preservation

The plants were collected, dried, preserved, and identified and confirmed in the Herbarium of Botany Department, University of Poonch Rawalakot. The voucher specimen has been submitted in the Herbarium Department of Botany, University of Poonch Rawalakot. The plants have been arranged alphabetically, showing their scientific and local names and local uses in Table 2.

Results and discussion

Documentation of medicinal plants

Plant species collected in the current study was used in treatment of various infections by the native

population of the area. Table 1 represents the demographic data of selected area informants whereas Table 2 providing information about 30 medicinal plants that belong to 21 families used for the treatment of 20 diseases. Current research is a struggle to account the ethnobotanical data on the basis of highly used medicinal plants with high rate to cure different diseases and their selection for searching of various bioactive compounds to treat these ailments.

Demographic data

According to the data the ratio of female and male informants were 63.3333% and 36.6667% respectively (Table 1). The informants were classified into three major groups on the basis of age, i.e., informants of 50 or 50+ years (16.6667%), 60 or 60+ years (33.3333%), 70 or 70+ years (50%). During the interview, it was detected that indigenous knowledge about the use of medicinal plants was more dominant in illiterate folks.

Family contribution

Rosaceae (6 species) is the predominant family according to number of species tailed by Pinaceae (3 species) and Moraceae, Asteraceae and Lamiaceae (2 species) while Juglandaceae, Ebenaceae, Punicaceae, Apiaceae, Amaranthaceae, Polygonaceae and remaining all other family contributed by one species towards species contribution. Maximum quantity of species showed by these families showed that the area under study is rich in biodiversity and the native people have considerable information of herbal medication prepared by these medicinal plants. Maximum family contribution is 20% by family Rosaceae followed by Pinaceae 10% and Moraceae, Asteraceae and Lamiaceae (7%) and all other species contribute 3% (Fig. 2). Rosaceae is largely described to possess significant bio-active constitute therefore contributing to the high use for medical remedies the results are match with findings of (Kidane *et al.*, 2018; Abbas *et al.*, 2017; Ashfaq *et al.*, 2019; Shaheen *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2013).

Table 1. Demographic information of the respondents

SL	Age group	Gender	No. of informants	Percentage%
1	50+	Male	1	3.3333%
		Female	4	13.3333%
2	60+	Male	5	16.6667%
		Female	5	16.6667%
3	70+	Male	5	16.6667%
		Female	10	33.3333%
Total		Male	11	36.6667%
		Female	19	63.3333%

Table 2. Medicinal plants description and their part use and disease categories

SL	Local name	Scientific name	Family	Parts used	Medicinal uses
1	Akhroot	<i>Juglans regia</i>	<i>Juglandaceae</i>	Fruit, leaves	Reduce risk of heart disease and cancer, improve brain health, and control uric acid, anti-diabetic.
2	Alubukhara	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Leaves, Fruit, Bark	Relieve constipation, Lower Blood sugar, improve bone health, healing wound.
3	Amlook	<i>Diospyrus kaki</i>	<i>Ebenaceae</i>	Leaves, Fruit	Treatment of hypertension, constipation.
4	Arwari	<i>Prunus persica</i>	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Fruit, Bark	Regulates blood sugar, prevents cancer, heals and enhance skin, promote hair growth.
5	Cheer	<i>Pinus roxburgai</i>	<i>Pinaceae</i>	Resin, Cone	Healing wound, Cone is used for the treatment of fungal infection.
6	Darona	<i>Punica granatum</i>	<i>Punicaceae</i>	Fruit, Bark	Lower level of blood pressure, fight against cancer, reduce joint pain, improve memory, fight against cancer, treat sore throats, urinary diseases, stomach related messes, skin issues
7	Derak	<i>Melia azzadirchta</i>	<i>Meliaceae</i>	Leaves	For skin treatment, anti-malarial.
8	Deyar	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>	<i>Pinaceae</i>	Wood, bark	Treat fever, urinary disorder, and diabetes.
9	Dhanya	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	Leaves, Seed	Treatment of Stomach pain, constipation, Gas, skin disease, and source of calcium.
10	Ganhaar	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Leaves, seed	Utilized as vegetables, saag. Crushed seed are blended in with rice water to control feminine cycle.
11	Halfari	<i>Rumax obtusifolius</i>	<i>Polygonaceae</i>	Leaves, Roots	The leaves are utilized as cure in the treatment of rankles. A tea produced using the roots has been utilized in the treatment of jaundice treatment of jaundice, whooping cough, boils and bleeding.
12	Hand	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Leaves	Reduce the pain of joints, Heart diseases; reduce stomach sensation, skin treatment and anti-diabetic.
13	Jand	<i>Ziziphus nummularia</i>	<i>Rhamnaceae</i>	Root, Bark	Used for cold, diarrhea, dysentery indigestion.
14	Kach mach	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Fruit, leaves	Used against dysentery and fever. Used for virginal infections.
15	Kangi	<i>Achellea melifolium</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Whole plant	Used as anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, blood tonic agent, urinary diseases, jaundice, piles, cleaning wounds, vaginal infection, allergy, anti-cancer.
16	Kankoli	<i>Elaeagnus parvifolia</i>	<i>Elaeagnaceae</i>	Fruit, Seed	Locally it is utilized as cardiovascular energizer, against diabetic, antipyretic, diuretic, likewise helpful to control hypertension. Vitamin C rich fruit is edible.
17	Khoobani	<i>Prunus armaniaca</i>	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Seed and Fruit	Used for asthma, constipation, infertility, vaginal infections.
18	Khroon	<i>Morus alba</i>	<i>Moraceae</i>	Fruits leaves	Treatment of Dizziness, liver and kidney disorders, inflammation.

19	Kiker	<i>Robinia pseudocacia</i>	<i>Fabiaceae</i>	Leaves, Flower, bark	The flowers are antispasmodic, aromatic, diuretic, and laxative. The leaf juice inhibits viruses.
20	Morpankh	<i>Thuja orientales</i>	<i>Cupressaceae</i>	Whole plant	Leaves used to treat a cough, fever, and headache. Oil is used for painful joints and muscles to increase blood circulation, reducing pain. Have antibacterial and anti-fungal properties.
21	Phagwara	<i>Ficus palmate</i>	<i>Moraceae</i>	Fruit, Leaves, Bark	It is utilized in the treatment of abdominal diseases and illnesses of lungs. Utilized in different sicknesses, for example gastrointestinal issues, hypoglycemia, growth, ulcer, diabetes.
22	Podina	<i>Mentha peprita</i>	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Leaves	Past of leaves applied over joints relieve pain, fresh juice with honey relieve cough and sore throat, used for the treatment of stomach pain.
23	Rair	<i>Pinus wallichaina</i>	<i>Pinaceae</i>	Resin, wood	The plant resin is utilized as a disinfectant and diuretic. Wood of <i>P. wallichiana</i> is valuable for cough, ulceration.
24	Rose	<i>Rosa indica</i>	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Leaves	Treatment of diarrhea, inflammation of mouth, oil used to treat dry skin.
25	Saib	<i>Malus pumila</i>	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Fruit, Root	Cure cancer, weight management, asthma and diabetes.
26	Sufaida	<i>Populus alba</i>	<i>Salicaceae</i>	Leaves, inner bark	Lower back pain, treatment of arthritis, reduce fever, and relieve pain of menstrual cramps.
27	Sumbol	<i>Berberis lysium</i>	<i>Berberidaceae</i>	Whole plant	Healing wound, treatment of jaundice, diabetes.
28	Tangi	<i>Pyrus pashia</i>	<i>Rosaceae</i>		The juice of the fruit is utilized in the treatment of diarrhea, management of gastrointestinal, respiratory, and vascular complications.
29	Thoom	<i>Allium satiuam</i>	<i>Amaryllidaceae</i>	Leaves, fruit	Lowering blood sugar and cholesterol, regulating blood pressure, effective against infections.
30	Timber	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Leaves, Seed	Improves digestion, improve memory, cure fever, thirst and heart diseases.

Fig 2. Family contribution to number of species within area

Mode of administration

Mode of administration of herbal medicinal plants was grouped into twenty classes (Fig. 3). The most frequent method of herbal remedies preparation was extract and extract, powder (13%) followed by extract and juice (10%), Juice and oil infusion (7%),) and remaining (juice, decoction), (Decoction), (Extract,

paste), (infusion, paste) and all other also contributed 3% towards total mode of administration. The current results are match with findings of Ahmad *et al.*, 2017; Shaheen *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2013).

The significant contribution of plant parts towards preparation of herbal medicines are shown in Fig. 4. Results showed that fruit and leaves, whole plant and leaves contributed more to medication. Maximum part contribution is followed by 20% (fruits and leaves) and 14% (leaves), 10% (Whole plant), (leaf, seeds) and 7% (Bark, fruit, leaf), (leaf, bark), (Fruit, bark),(Resin, leaf) While remaining contributed 3% in herbal remedy. The current outcomes are matched with findings of (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017; Shaheen *et al.*, 2017; Abbas *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2013; Hussain *et al.*, 2006).

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